

THE ROLE OF FAIRY TALES IN THE TEACHING OF ENGLISH

Temirova Dilfuza Ziyodullayevna

School 36 teacher

Saidehsonova Qamaraxon Usmonovna

SamSIFL, student

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Abstract There are numerous diverse ways to learn English. Each method is useful both for adults and children. You'll likely guess that English fairy tales are the foremost successful instrument with the assistance of which dialect learning gets to be a fun movement. This paper aims to display the benefits of fairy tales.

Keywords: fairy tale, children, method, interest, games

Nowadays, English language is second language in the world. The reason is that great attention is paid to learning English in our country. Learners learn this language through multimedia, with the assistance of books, dictionary and fairy tales. In the education, it is very necessary to interest children. The English teacher contains an exceptionally vital task not only to teach and educate the language, but also to create an interest in its study. Because teaching this subject is very complicated for elementary school children. They get bored and tired quickly. It is very difficult to keep the attention of young children. They are interested in fun and playful lessons. Albert Einstein expressed this opinion about the fairy tale: "If you want your children to be intelligent, read them fairy tales. If you want them to be more intelligent, read them more fairy tales." The use of fairy tales in teaching is of great help to the teacher. Fairy tales are an awesome and important source for English language lessons. They are fun, pleasant and brief. With the assistance of fairy tales, children learn distinctive language viewpoints: linguistic use, modern vocabulary and in expansion to that, fairy tales can impact emphatically on children's interest in books.

Firstly, fairy tales help to expand children's imagination, because interesting stories in fairy tales encourage them to imagine. Children imagine scary, funny and sad stories from fairy tales by reading or watching cartoons based on them.

Secondly, children learn English words easily with the help of fairy tales. They are useful not only for children but also for all learners. Because of this, language learners will quickly lose their minds if they try to learn a language by grammar or memorizing words. Easy sentences in fairy tales will help them learn English quickly. Another useful aspect of fairy tales is that they expand children's worldview. The content of the fairy tales of all nations is the same, that is, they all encourage to do good. For example, "Zumrad and Qimmat" in the Uzbek people, "Zolushka" in the Russian people, and "Cinderella" in the English people have the same content. The main characters of these stories have difficulties at the beginning of the story. But they are happy at the end because of their patience. From these fairy tales, children learn to be patient with difficulties, to be open-minded, to return evil with evil, and good with good. By reading fairy tales, English learners get to know the customs, culture, and national clothes of that nation.

The unquestionable merits of fairy tales are:

- 1) Genuineness
- 2) Enlightening abundance
- 3) Concentration of phonetic implies

4) Passionate affect on understudies

Taking into account the above advantages of the fairy tale, it is possible to organize the following games from the fairy tale during the lesson:

1. The role- playing games

In this type of game , children are divided into groups and show scenes based on fairy tales. The role-playing game helps children to better understand the fairy tale

2. Silent action games -Pantomimo . The type of game helps children understand each other easily without words.

3."Brainstorming " method. The main purpose of this method is to identify the characters of fairy tales .In this type, more children make sentences with adjectives and thereby increase their vocabulary.

4."Journey to the world of fairy tales" . The type of game is very important and interesting . Children are mainly required to expand their thinking and imagination. In this type of game , children have an imaginary conversation with fairy-tale characters with their eyes closed and they need the teacher to find answers to the following questions:

Who is it?

What questions did he ask him and why? and so on.

By passing the lesson on the basis of games, teachers achieve their goals .In addition, it is possible to increase their interest in the English language by giving children cartoons based on fairy tales, because every child is different. Some children don't like to read , instead they are more interested in watching cartoons and movies .Some children like reading the fairy tale itself , not watching the cartoon. Therefore , the teacher must take into account the interests of all children.

Children try hard to understand fairy tales and cartoons because interesting stories in them attract children's attention. So that, while watching or reading a fairytale or cartoon they try to find the translation of unfamiliar words in them ,which is the first helper to increase their vocabulary and learn English well.

Based on the above, it is worth concluding that fairy tales are very important method and precious resource when teaching and learning foreign language. With their helps, learners improve listening, reading, and comprehension skills and increase vocabulary

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